

ASIC Architecture and Implementation of RED Scheduler for Mixed-Criticality Real-Time Systems

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Abstract—This paper presents a new ASIC design of a coprocessor that performs process scheduling for embedded mixed-criticality real-time systems consisting of processes of various criticality and various real-time attributes. The proposed solution is implementing Robust Earliest Deadline (RED) algorithm and previously developed hardware architectures used for scheduling of real-time processes. Thanks to the on-chip implementation of the scheduler in a form of a coprocessor, the scheduler operations can be completed in two clock cycles regardless of the process amount within the system contains. The proposed scheduler was verified by simulations that applied millions of random inputs. Chip area costs are evaluated by synthesis into an ASIC using 28 nm process by TSMC. Two versions of real-time process schedulers were compared: EDF scheduler designed for hard real-time processes only and the proposed RED scheduler. The RED algorithm handles variations of process execution times better, achieves higher CPU utilization and can be used for scheduling of hard real-time, soft real-time and non-real-time processes combined within one system that is not possible using the other scheduling algorithms.

Keywords—scheduling, mixed-criticality, ASIC, RED.

I. INTRODUCTION

Real-time (RT) embedded systems are systems that execute RT processes, also known as RT tasks. Successful execution of a real-time process depends not only on the correct results of the computation inside the process but on the time when the process is finished as well. Even if we use a processor that disposes the highest performance, there is no guarantee that all RT processes are finished before their deadlines. Therefore, a process scheduler that is taking into consideration process deadlines must be used [1].

Ideally, RT process schedulers always create an optimum schedule with the best possible order of processes so that all processes will be finished before their deadlines. In addition to that, an ideal process scheduler introduces a minimum CPU overhead, which means that the CPU time is consumed for the scheduled processes, not their scheduling. An ideal scheduling should not only consume minimum CPU time, this time should be a constant time too! In fact, this requirement is the most important because only this way, it can be guaranteed that the whole RT system remains deterministic and well-predictable [1-3].

The major motivation to implement a process scheduler in ASIC is that the software (SW) implemented process

schedulers are usually based on user-defined priorities, not the actual deadlines of processes. Therefore, these SW schedulers are not enough robust nor efficient enough for deterministic support of processes of various criticality levels that furthermore are combined in the same system (without hypervisor). Luckily, process scheduling algorithms can be accelerated by hardware (HW) in order to meet the performance and determinism requirements [1].

Another problem is that the existing schedulers implemented in HW are generally applied in only simple systems that consist of hard RT processes only. These solutions are not suitable enough for RT systems with higher complexity, robustness, size and with variety of process types that are mixed within the same system. Thus, a more robust scheduler supporting various types of processes is required. Such a scheduler can be achieved by implementing and existing algorithm called Robust Earliest Deadline (RED), which is designed for handling of system overheads [1-10].

Mixed-criticality is an active research field, as reflected in the review by Burns and Davis [11]. Mixed-criticality is resulting from the global trend in microelectronics that lies in increasing integration of growing number of components on chip belonging to safety-critical domain. Until not so long time, process isolation was required within safety-critical certification to imply performing of critical processes in a separated hardware. Due to the process isolation, RT systems were under-utilized and based on the pessimistic analysis of worst-case execution time for each process. As average execution time is generally significantly smaller than the worst-case time, CPU resources are usually reserved much more than it is really needed for execution of RT processes [12-15].

Mixed-criticality RT systems can contain any combination of critical and/or non-critical processes in the same platform without complete isolation of the processes as it is considered to be too inefficient (e.g. using hypervisors). Non-isolation is recommended as a demanding and efficient way to improve CPU utilization, which is achieved by executing low-priority and non-critical processes within slack time that becomes available whenever high-priority and high-critical processes are finished sooner than it was predicted according to worst-case execution time. This is happening relatively frequently in real-world applications. The problem is that safety-critical processes and best-effort processes have usually conflicting requirements, being an important research challenge [16-18].

The topic of mixed-criticality is considered as a very active research field, which is mentioned in the review from Burns and Davis. The mixed-criticality research is trying to solve the problem of scheduling policies that are supposed to maximize CPU utilization and simultaneously to maintain the schedulability of every safety-critical process [11].

II. RELATED WORK

One of the most popular scheduling algorithms for RT systems is Earliest Deadline First (EDF), which is proven to always create an optimum schedule for systems containing hard RT processes only [1, 2]. The main idea of this algorithm is to order all processes according to their deadlines in such a way so that a process with the earliest deadline is the process that should be executed first. The processes that are ready for execution are stored in a structure called “process queue”. Process queues can be implemented by various sorting architectures, such as shift registers architecture [19] or systolic array architecture [20].

In our previous work published in [21-24], we already presented novel RT process schedulers implemented in a form of coprocessors. A slightly modified EDF algorithm was used to support killing of processes according to their ID, which is important in recent operating systems. The possibility to kill any process in the system according to the process ID increases flexibility and extensibility of the proposed solution, such as process synchronization and support of non-RT processes.

Beside of our research, there have been also other solutions presented. One solution employs EDF algorithm with the maximum number of processes being 64 [25], and the other approach uses priorities instead of deadlines, which is less efficient for RT systems in terms of CPU utilization [26]. There are other solutions based on priorities or static scheduling [8-10, 27-29] as well. These solutions are suitable for systems consisting of hard RT processes only.

Since various types of processes may co-exist together in complex RT mixed-criticality system, a requirement for a robust process scheduler that supports all types of processes arises. For this reason, we decided to create an ASIC-based process scheduler that implements Robust Earliest Deadline (RED) algorithm, which is suitable for all types of processes [1].

The RED algorithm is an extension of the EDF algorithm. Both algorithms are performing sorting of processes based on process deadlines, which is shown in Fig. 1. EDF accepts all requests for adding and scheduling a freshly created process, but RED is predicting if any of the processes is able to miss a deadline and if so, then it chooses the most suitable process to temporarily reject it and move it to Reject queue. By this, we can guarantee that all hard RT processes always meet deadlines and additionally, as many soft RT processes as possible meet deadlines too. In case when any of the ready processes is finished sooner than the worst-case timing analysis predicts, and there is sufficient free time to reclaim and finish on time any of the rejected processes, then RED uses its reclaiming policy for moving one of the rejected processes back from Reject Queue to the Ready queue [1, 2].

The method for monitoring of execution time of RT processes and prediction of their deadline misses was also presented in [30-32].

Fig. 1. EDF (a) and RED (b) scheduling algorithms [1].

III. PROPOSED RED SCHEDULER

A. Top module

Fig. 2 shows a top module of the proposed scheduler represents a coprocessor that contains 3 components: Ready Queue, Control Unit and Reject Queue.

The top module has only one input (called INSTR) – the instruction provided by CPU. There are two types of instructions: *schedule_process* and *kill_process*.

The output of the top module is PROCESS_TO_RUN, which provides information back to CPU about which process is selected by the scheduler for execution at the moment.

Fig. 2. Top module of RED scheduler.

B. Ready Queue

This component is based on an existing sorting architecture called Shift Registers, which consists of process cells. Each process cell contains one process comparator, control logic and a register to store one process. The process cells can exchange processes with adjacent process cells. Each

process cell receives the same instruction in parallel from the shared bus. An example of the Shift Registers with four cells is given in Fig. 3 [19].

Fig. 3. Shift Registers [19].

The Ready Queue component was extended by a feature called Overload Analysis by applying the following changes:

1. Extend each process cell with register for execution time
2. Add overload detection into each process cell
3. Add combination of overload bits for all process cells
4. Add victim selection

Change 1 is to insert an execution time register into every process cell within the Ready queue component. It is used as a remaining worst-case execution time for the actual process cell + the sum of the remaining worst-case execution times of all processes that are scheduled before the actual process.

If a new process is inserted to the process cell, then the new value of the execution time register is calculated by adding the worst-case execution time of the new process + the value of the execution time register stored in the process cell located before the actual process cell, where the new process is supposed to be inserted. In addition to this, the worst-case execution time value of the new process is added to the execution time registers of all processes scheduled behind the new process.

In an existing process is removed from Ready queue, then all processes that are scheduled behind the removed process must decrease the values of execution time registers by the current value of execution time register of the removed process.

Change 2 is to implement a logic that calculates the overload bit of every process cell. The logic checks whether the worst-case execution time of the new process + the value stored in the execution time register of the actual process cell is greater than the deadline value of the actual process. If yes, then scheduling the new process before the process in the actual process cell can cause the actual process to miss its deadline. This situation is called overload and the overload bit of the corresponding process cell is set to high in such a situation.

Change 3 is to add an OR gate within the Ready queue component but outside of the process cells. The OR gate takes as input all overload bits provided from the process cells. If at least one overload bit is '1', then the OR gate output is '1' too,

meaning that the system is overloaded. This result is then given to the Control Unit component via RDQ_TO_CU.

Change 4 is to add a logic that selects one process within the ready processes stored in the Ready Queue component. The selected process is removed from Ready Queue and inserted to Reject Queue. This process is called "victim process" as well because it is sacrificed by the scheduler because the system would be overloaded otherwise.

C. Control Unit

This component is responsible for controlling Reject Queue and Ready Queue components. Whenever a new valid instruction is provided from CPU, Control Unit performs this instruction by forwarding it to Ready Queue. If no instruction is provided from CPU, Control Unit can automatically move processes between Reject Queue and Ready to maximize the number of processes to be executed on time but to keep the system to be not overloaded.

Whenever the system is overloaded (i.e. in overload state), the Control Unit gives an order to remove one process within the processes stored in Ready Queue (called a victim) and to store this process to Reject Queue. The victim is chosen according to priority values and position of the process within the Ready Queue in such a way that the process with the lowest priority within those processes that are located before the first process reporting the overload is chosen as the victim.

Whenever an existing process is killed (i.e. removed from the Ready Queue) and the system is not overloaded, the Control Unit tries to reclaim one process from Reject Queue. Thus, one process is selected among the processes in Reject Queue and moved back to Ready Queue. Then, the overload state is checked again. Control Unit moves back the reclaimed process from Ready Queue to Reject Queue if the system is overloaded again. However, the reclaiming is successful and the reclaimed process remains in the Ready Queue if the system is not overloaded.

There are 4 criticality levels supported by the proposed scheduler. They are used for the rejection and reclaiming policy described above. These 4 criticality levels are defined by 2 bits the following way:

- "00" – non-RT processes and soft RT processes with low priority
- "01" – soft RT processes with medium priority
- "10" – soft RT processes with high priority
- "11" – safety-critical hard RT processes

D. Reject Queue

The Reject Queue component is a queue that consists of rejected processes. These processes are ordered in such a way that the process with the highest priority and the latest deadline is selected and sent to output of the queue. The selection of such a process is performed in 1 clock cycle. The Reject Queue is an implementation of Shift Registers architecture, just like the Ready Queue but without the new changes performed only for Ready Queue. Also, the Shift Registers architecture is configured as a MAX queue.

Every Reject Queue item is mapped 1:1 to one rejected process. The items of the Shift Registers are ordered according to a value that is a combination of two values that are concatenated: process priority and process deadline. The process priority is used for the higher bits and the process deadline is used for the lower bits. Thus, process priority has higher importance than process deadline when choosing which process is supposed to be reclaimed as the next one.

Shift Registers can remove any process depending on the given process ID. However, this feature is not needed for Reject Queue component because only the process that is at the output of the queue is always removed. Thus, the Reject Queue component was simplified to always extract the 1st process only.

IV. VERIFICATION

The proposed RED scheduler was described using SystemVerilog language. This language was used to verify the proposed solution in simulations as well. These simulations are based on Universal Verification Methodology in principle, but only using the SystemVerilog language without any UVM libraries. One UVM transaction is mapped to 1 instruction, which takes 2 clock cycles to execute. No UVM agents were needed for interfacing of DUT (Design Under Test).

We created one test procedure can randomly generate instructions for DUT input and one predictor that is predicting expected outputs of DUT. The expected outputs provided by predictor are compared to the real output of DUT and the comparison results are written to scoreboard.

Our test procedure generates millions of instructions consisting of fixed instruction opcodes and process IDs but random process deadlines, worst-case execution times and real execution times.

The predictor generates expected outputs of the DUT according to the instructions sent to DUT input. The predictor logic is described in a pure sequential manner (same as a software) using much higher level of abstraction as well. For example, our predictor adopts existing SystemVerilog keyword called *queue* and a built-in function for processes sorting called *sort()*.

Correct behavior of the proposed solution was verified by several millions of test cycles, each consisting of 1000 instructions. One half is *schedule_process* and the second half is *kill_process*. Full capacities of the Ready Queue and Reject Queue were tested. The DUT output and expected output from predictor were the same for 100% of used instructions.

V. SYNTHESIS RESULTS

The proposed RED scheduler and original EDF scheduler were both synthesized into TSMC 28nm high performance mobile (HPM) technology using Cadence Genus. A clock frequency of 500 MHz and the power supply of 0.9 V were used for the synthesis. The static timing analysis report contained no negative setup slack after the synthesis.

The chip area costs of the EDF scheduler and RED scheduler are presented in Table I. The Maximum Number of

Processes column defines the maximum number of processes supported by the synthesized scheduler, which is equal to the Ready Queue size. The chip area cost of EDF scheduler and RED scheduler are presented in column EDF Chip Area and RED Chip Area, respectively. Table I also shows a relative overhead (in column Overhead), which represents a relative increase of chip area cost caused by extending the EDF scheduler into RED scheduler.

Both schedulers use the minimum required process ID bit width, e.g. 3 for 8 processes or 5 for 32 processes. The obtained results show that the RED scheduler has notably higher chip area cost, which is caused by the fact that the RED scheduler implements significantly more complex algorithm.

TABLE I. CHIP AREA COST OF EDF AND RED WITH VARIOUS MAXIMUM NUMBER OF PROCESSES

Maximum Number of Processes	EDF Chip Area [μm^2]	RED Chip Area [μm^2]	Overhead
8	1702	13214	+676,38%
16	3637	28531	+684,47%
24	5979	50218	+739,91%
32	9085	69389	+663,78%
40	13307	92389	+594,29%
48	19387	108522	+459,77%
56	26787	130421	+386,88%
64	33340	146146	+338,35%

The power consumption results are presented in Table II. These results represent the total power consumption that consists of the leakage and dynamic power. The dynamic power consumption was calculated using an average toggle rate of every bit in the chip, which is not very precise metric because the real power consumption would depend a lot on the frequency and order of coprocessor instruction calls. However, the same test case with the same toggle rate of bits was applied for both, EDF and RED schedulers. Therefore, the comparison is still valid and relevant. As one can see from the table, these power consumption results are proportionally similar to the increase of chip area cost that was already presented in Table I. The dependency between the chip area results and power consumption results is apparently linear.

TABLE II. POWER CONSUMPTION OF EDF AND RED WITH VARIOUS MAXIMUM NUMBER OF PROCESSES

Maximum Number of Processes	EDF Power Consumption [μW]	RED Power Consumption [μW]	Overhead
8	2044	12121	+493,00%

Maximum Number of Processes	EDF Power Consumption [μ W]	RED Power Consumption [μ W]	Overhead
16	3809	25913	+580,31%
24	6356	43373	+582,39%
32	9881	66559	+573,61%
40	14711	77434	+426,37%
48	20693	93948	+354,01%
56	28263	115748	+309,54%
64	36535	124162	+239,84%

The overall comparison of the EDF and the novel RED schedulers is presented in Table III. The support of all types of processes and their combinations in one scheduler is provided at a cost of higher chip area and power consumption.

TABLE III. COMPARISON OF EDF AND RED SCHEDULERS

Criterion	Selected Scheduler	
	EDF	RED
Chip area	A	(4.38 – 8.40) x A
Power	P	(3.40 – 5.82) x P
Execution time	2 clock cycles	2 clock cycles
Hard RT processes	yes	yes
Soft RT processes	no	yes
Non-RT processes	yes	yes
Mixed-criticality supported	no	yes

The presented results showed that the proposed RED scheduler requires from three to five times higher chip area than the EDF scheduler. On the other hand, the RED scheduler is much more robust since supporting of hard RT processes and soft RT processes is provided simultaneously.

Both schedulers perform their operations in the same constant time, which is only 2 clock cycles. Thus, the latency and throughput remain unchanged. The presented schedulers can be applied for periodic and sporadic processes the same way as for the aperiodic processes.

VI. FUTURE IMPROVEMENTS

The RED scheduler was optimized for RT systems that are using single-core CPUs only. However, the scheduler can be extended to support two or four CPU cores simultaneously by

applying the same approaches that were already used for EDF based schedulers [9-12].

Further improvements can be achieved by adding hardware-accelerated management of periodic processes (i.e. automatic rescheduling of periodic processes after each period), inter-process communication and process synchronization.

Additionally, an optimization of the scheduler in order to make it more scalable with respect to the maximum number of processes would be beneficial too, especially with focus on increasing the maximum clock frequency of the design.

VII. CONCLUSION

We proposed a new process scheduler that performs RED scheduling algorithm and is implemented on chip. The proposed scheduler is suitable for robust mixed-criticality RT systems due to the ability to distinguish between various types of processes, including their priority and deadlines. The proposed solution used an approach of reusing and extending of existing EDF schedulers. The Ready Queue as well as the Reject Queue (i.e. both queues) is implemented using an existing sorting architecture called Shift Registers. Both queues perform an operation of process insertion or process removal in constant time (1 clock cycle) regardless of number of processes used in the system. The RED algorithm extended the EDF algorithm with two features: rejection of process and reclaiming of process reclaiming. These features are combined with a possibility to use various types of processes and various criticality levels.

The RED scheduler correctly and efficiently handles any combination of safety-critical hard RT processes, high-priority soft RT processes, medium-priority soft RT processes, low-priority soft RT processes and non-RT processes. This means that all safety-critical hard RT processes meet their deadlines, and as many as possible soft RT processes meet their deadlines, considering the priority within the soft RT processes as well. Therefore, the proposed RED scheduler is very suitable for mixed-criticality RT systems.

The RED scheduler is providing 1024 priority levels for the non-RT processes and 4 criticality levels for the RT processes. The 4 criticality levels are dividing RT processes to the abovementioned hard RT, high-priority soft RT, medium-priority soft RT and low-priority soft RT processes. Thus, there are 1028 levels of criticality in total (1024 + 4). The priority level, type of task, deadline value and worst-case execution time are provided from system (CPU + operating system + user) to the proposed scheduler via coprocessor interface.

The proposed solution is consuming higher, but still acceptable resource costs, (i.e. chip area and power consumption) which are scaling still linearly with growing maximum number of processes. If we compare the proposed solution to existing solutions implemented in software, the ASIC implementation is able to execute instructions (*schedule_process* and *kill_process*) in constant time (2 clock cycles) and with dramatically higher throughput. Thanks to that, the system using the proposed RED scheduler would be much more efficient and deterministic, resulting in lower amount of processes missing their deadlines, especially if they

are high-criticality processes. The ASIC-implemented scheduler causes CPUs to waste minimum possible time for scheduling and to focus only on execution of the scheduled processes instead.

The proposed process scheduler is not intended to fully replace existing software implementations of kernels. Instead of that, it is supposed to be combined with existing software-implemented operating systems in a reasonable way.

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